

Abstraction, Indexing Process, and Identification for Bibliographic Methods, and Reprints

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Abstract:

Abstraction, Indexing Process, and Identification are one of important topics, which if explained would be bluffy, but are essential for Bibliographical Methods, and the way we do handle any data, for convinieny in making archival records. Anything, when we do rely on past tense as per our grammer would be archived materials, beginning from our thoughts as well as works. Thus, In this paper, we shall attempt to discuss, how we can make our archives of published materials more systematic in online as well as offline medium.

Keywords: Abstraction, Indexing, Bibliography, Archival of Data, Arjun Dahal, arjundahalard

Introduction:

Abstraction, Indexing, as well as Bibliographical methods aren't new topics, and author does expects similiar from readers, to avoid making paper lengthier. Thus we shall begin to discuss from a journal article, as Journals and Periodicals are places, where authors do seek, to publish their work.

These days, we rely on DOI number, assigned to each published works, and do rely on standard formats of citation techniues for Referencing like as MLA, APA, BibTex, Chigago Manual style, Harvard, and much more.

Question that does immediately arises is, does Libraries keep, each of our documents, archived as per standard citation techniques, or not?

If answer is no, then we are following some rules of citation techniques for referencing, to maintain proper Bibliographic records, as even Libraries would need methods, to classify the books, hooking to the term of properly cited or not, relying on standards as per citation techniques and referencing methods.

To make answer yes, we still would need to make topics like as departments, to address citation as per various citation techniques. That would be hazardous, when, a same source is cited, as per convinieny

of users, by means of same various formats, as same data would repeatedly be archived, consuming more space, allowing us to argue about keeping multiple sources safely, by allowing multiple users to access any materials, which would be blazing advantage, if we are able to do with resources, and budgetary means.

Abstraction and Metadata:

We generally find, abstracts and their citation, which is talked as allowing readers to read abstracts, provided that abstracts have provided meaning of work, to be understood by readers.

Problem would be raised, when moralness would put question, does all authors read the complete papers, documents, and articles completely, to address question, why was abstract and citation details provided for free, by discussing about standard access, and types open access, so that, works can be cited as per study.

Indexing:

Indexing is quite similar to that of keeping things indexed in a record file. That would again put question of how we do rely on abstraction of metadata, that is generally talked as partialness, and completeness, and author does doubt, if entire contents are properly abstracted and indexed or not.

Differences then would create problem. Metadata when are indexed, would provide us partial information, where as when complete data is provided, then we don't need partial metadata, as we have access to complete data. Then too repetition has to be studied for partial data and complete data.

Identification Methods:

We rely on various identifiers, like as DOI that we discussed in beginning of our paper, which does identifies any document based on numerical values. ISBN numbers, ISSN numbers, and lot of numerical based methods can be found.

Necessity of study occurs, when we do make collection, or publish in different means, with different identifiers. An example can be discussed, like as collection of articles where each article has separate DOI number, when is made as book, then ISBN number would be new identifier. Similarly, when published in series, or is made like as journal, then ISSN number would be needed, different then of previous publisher's ISSN number, and if DOI again be assigned to book, or series of ISSN, then that too would be unique.

Bibliographic Methods:

Identification methods that we discussed, would then raise problems in Bibliographic methods, and for referencing, due to reprints, then due to techniques of citations for referencing.

Are our Libraries, then be able to provide us with cataloguing of data, based on Bibliographic methods, addressing reprints, as well as archival, might put question on database and security for database, along with archival for perpetuity, where as identification of author and publishers too would put important questions as per various identifiers for individual person, and for organizations and institutions, would be another question for accuracy in referencing, identification, bibliographical methods and cataloguing of datas for archival process.

Possible Convinient Means:

Computing tools, when are made rigorous, allowing to identify and work for listing would be convinient for online medium and in Internet for any authors and publishers, where as offline Libraries would still need to work manually, keeping records of each authors and publishers

Actknowledgement:

Author actknowledges Springer Publication, and other publications, which had already began to use multiple identifers for publications like as assigning DOI to book with ISBN, then even ISSN, as found in their websites and does actknowledges his own application letters written to Tribhuvan University's Central Library, and various Libraries of Nepal, though I don't know, if they have begun abstraction and indexing, by including various identifiers like as OCLC numbers and lot of other identifiers.